

Impact of Visual Merchandising on Impulse Buying Behaviour for Women's Clothing In The Lens of Kano's Attractive Quality Theory

Author's Details:

Abbas Dadras¹, Somaye Hematian², and Mohammad Jashn Sadeh³

¹ Assistance Professor, Collage of Humanities, Department of Business, Islamic Azad University, Bandar Abbas Branch, Hormozgan, Iran

² Master of Business Management Student, Majoring in E-commerce, Graduate School, Collage of Humanities, Department of Business, Islamic Azad University, Bandar Abbas Branch, Hormozgan, Iran

³ Master of Business Management Student, Majoring in E-commerce, Graduate School, Collage of Humanities, Department of Business, Islamic Azad University, Bandar Abbas Branch, Hormozgan, Iran

*Corresponding author: Email: Abbas_dadras@yahoo.com

Abstract:

Studying women could be interesting as shopping is the accepted domain of women; however, modern social and demographic movements challenge traditional gender roles within the family structure. This study aims to understand the women's impulsive buying behavior and attempt to know how attractive store visual merchandising play a significant role in their shopping for clothes. In other words, the authors intend to study components of visual merchandising impact in store design on impulsive women's buying behavior with a focus on recognition of their preferences. The study is based on Kano's attractive quality theory. The paper uses primary data and source of the data is Kano's questionnaire which is filled by the respondent. Target population of the research study is those people who are coming for shopping in malls, retail stores in Bandar Abbas city, Islamic republic of Iran. The study only focuses on the quantitative research. Although the research study focused only for impulsive buying for women's clothing but many other things can be considered. Data analysis has been done through SPSS software. The study results of Kano's model show the wide range of customer preferences towards store design which can provoke the impulse buying behavior of women's.

Keywords: Impulse buying, Consumer behavior, Store design, Kano's attractive theory

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1. Visual Merchandising

Merchandising is a marketing practice in which the brand or image from one product or service is used to sell another. Visual merchandising refers to the use and manipulation of attractive sales displays and retail floor plans to engage customers and boost sales activity. In visual merchandising, the products being sold are typically displayed in such a way as to attract consumers from the intended market by drawing attention to the product's best features and benefits.

Visual merchandising is the activity and profession of developing floor plans and three-dimensional displays in order to maximize sales.

Both goods and services can be displayed to highlight their features and benefits. The purpose of such visual merchandising is to attract, engage and motivate the customer towards making a purchase [4].

Visual merchandising commonly occurs in retail spaces such as retail stores and trade shows. Visual merchandising builds upon or augments the retail design of a store. It is one of the final stages in setting out a store in a way customers find attractive and appealing. Many elements can be used by visual merchandisers in creating displays including colour, lighting, space, product information, sensory inputs (such as smell, touch, and sound), as well as technologies such as digital displays and interactive installations.

The purpose of visual merchandising is to:

- 1) Make it easier for the customer to locate the desired category and merchandise.
- 2) Make it easier for the customer to self-select. Make it possible for the shopper to co-ordinate.
- 3) Recommend, highlight and demonstrate particular products at strategic locations.
- 4) Educate the customer about the product in an effective and creative way.

Visual merchandising is offered to the customer through exterior and interior presentation. Each should be coordinated with the other using the store's overall theme. Creating and maintaining a store's visual merchandising plan, however, is not a simple task. It is necessary to continuously determine what the customer sees. This evaluation from the customer's perspective should start on the exterior and work completely through the interior of the store. The art of increasing the sale of products by effectively and sensibly displaying them at the retail outlet is called as visual merchandising [4].

Visual merchandising refers to the aesthetic display of the merchandise to attract the potential buyers, prompt them to buy and eventually increase the sales of the store. In simpler words, visual merchandising is the art of displaying the merchandise to influence the consumer's buying behavior. The store must offer a positive

ambience to the customers, so that they will enjoy their shopping [5].

In the present paper, the most important visual merchandising attributes of the study include: store layout, mannequins, point of purchase display, atmospherics, lighting, music, scent, window display, colour, graphics, photography and signage, seasonal displays, fashion trends.

1.2. Impulse Buying

Impulse buying is a major research concern among researchers due to its pervasive aspects of consumer behavior as well as its mystery in the marketing world. The research studies on consumers buying behavior keep on struggling to give a better definition for impulse buying behavior of consumers over last five decades [1]. Studying women could be interesting as shopping is the accepted domain of women. Women has specific influence on impulse buying such as women tend to be more impulsive than men. If consumers are in a good mood, they tend to reward themselves more generously and tend to be more impulsive. Women involve themselves in a more thorough analysis of message content and display a greater sensitivity to the details of information when making judgments. Suganya S & Beena Joice [8] stated that impulse is unplanned, the result of an exposure to a stimulus and is decided on the-spot. Consumers are influenced by internal and external factors that triggers their impulse purchase behavior. Impulse purchase or impulse buying is an unplanned or otherwise spontaneous purchase. Impulse items can be anything, a new product, samples or well-established products at surprising low prices. Customer who has to not preplanning to purchase product they have to see product and they decided to purchase. Purchasing is, generally defined as, a consumer’s unplanned purchase which is an important part of buyer behavior. An impulse purchase or impulse buy is an unplanned decision to buy a product or service, made just before a purchase [7]. In recent years, with the advancement of women’s economic status and self-conscience, impulsive buying has increased. Therefore, it is important to learn the factors which determine female consumers’ impulsive cosmetics purchases.

1.3. The Theory of Attractive Quality

Inspired by Herzberg’s M-H theory in behavioral science, Kano and his coworkers developed the theory of attractive quality. The theory of attractive quality is useful to better understand different aspects of how customers evaluate a product or offering [2]. Over the past two decades, this theory has gained exposure and acceptance through articles in various marketing, quality, and

operations management journals. The theory of attractive quality has been applied in strategic thinking, business planning, and product development to demonstrate lessons learned in innovation, competitive- ness, and product compliance [3].

According to Kano (2001), the theory of attractive quality originated because of the lack of explanatory power of a one-dimensional recognition of quality. For instance, people are satisfied if the packaging of rice has cooking instructions and dissatisfied if the packaging does not have cooking instructions. For a quality attribute such as religious symbols & images, people are not satisfied if the package does not religious symbols & images, but they are very dissatisfied if it does. To understand the role of quality attributes, Kano et al. (1984) present a model that evaluates patterns of quality, based on customers’ satisfaction with specific quality attributes and their degree of sufficiency [2]. On the horizontal axis in the Kano diagram (Fig1) the physical sufficiency of a certain quality attribute is displayed. The vertical axis shows satisfaction with a certain quality attribute (Kano et al. 1984). The theory explains how the relationship between the degree of sufficiency and customer satisfaction with a quality attribute can be classified into five categories of perceived quality. According to Kano et al. (1984), their ideas are similar to quality theories suggested by Mizuno and Ishikawa. But instead of only providing general concepts and nomenclature, Kano and his coworkers provide a methodology to use [3].

Figure 1: An Overview of the Theory of Attractive Quality

The categories of perceived quality are:

Attractive Quality

Attractive quality attributes can be described as a surprise and delight attributes; they provide satisfaction when achieved fully, but do not cause dissatisfaction when not fulfilled (Kano et al. 1984). These are attributes that are not normally expected, for example, a maintenance instructions on a package of rice showing the better storage of the rice. Since these types of quality attributes often unexpectedly delight customers, they are often unspoken. An example of this is W. Edwards Deming's rather bantered statement: "The customer never asked Mr. Edison for a light bulb" [6]. Researchers have emphasized the importance of attractive quality creation (Kano 2001) since this dimension has been somewhat neglected by quality specialists, who have tended to focus on how to eliminate things gone wrong [6]. In a similar sense, Cole (2001) suggests that the understanding of continuous improvement should be widened to continuous innovation and include concepts such as exploration and discontinuous innovation [6].

One-dimensional Quality

One-dimensional quality attributes result in satisfaction when fulfilled and dissatisfaction when not fulfilled (Kano et al. 1984). These attributes are spoken and are those with which companies compete (Gustafsson 1998). For example, providing rice in "Metal Cans" is likely to result in customer satisfaction, but if there is not, it is likely that the customer will feel misled, which results in dissatisfaction [2].

Must-be Quality

Must-be quality attributes are taken for granted when fulfilled, but result in dissatisfaction when not fulfilled (Kano et al. 1984). For example, consumers are dissatisfied when the rice package is not in "Cotton Bag", but when it's designed the result is not increased customer satisfaction. Since customers expect these attributes and views them as basic, it is unlikely that they are going to tell the company about them when asked about quality attributes. They assume that companies understand these product design fundamentals [2].

Indifferent Quality

Indifferent quality refers to aspects that are neither good nor bad, and, consequently, they do not result in either customer satisfaction or customer dissatisfaction [2].

Reverse Quality

Reverse quality refers to a high degree of achievement resulting in dissatisfaction (and vice versa, a low degree of achievement resulting in satisfaction) and to the fact that not all customers are alike [2].

2. MATERIAL AND METHODS

2.1. Study location

This study was conducted in three malls in Bandar Abbas city, Islamic republic of Iran. The malls include: Zeiton, Southern Star and City Center.

2.2. Population and Sample

Data were collected through a questionnaire that was implemented in person through interviews with 190 female consumers randomly (20-45 years old) who suddenly decided to buy from a store in one of the maintained malls.

2.3. Questionnaire

The questionnaire was divided into two parts: background questions (gender, age, education, and so on). Kano pair questions. In addition to the questionnaire, a letter that explained the purpose of the survey was included. The Kano questionnaire contained pairs of customer requirement questions [6]. Each question had two parts:

1. "How do you feel if that feature is present in the product?" (This is the functional form of the question.)
2. "How do you feel if that feature is not present in the product?" (This is the dysfunctional form of the question.) [2].

Each part of the question, the customer could answer chosen one of five alternatives exemplified in (Fig 2). According to Berger et al. (1993), the wording of the alternatives is the most critical choice made in the Kano methodology [2]. The chosen wording of the alternatives adapted from Berger et al. (1993) (that is, "I like it that way," "It must be that way," "I am neutral," "I can live with it that way," "I dislike it that way") is similar to the Japanese version suggested by Kano et al. (1984).

The classification of attributes described previously is made based on the pair questions. Each quality attributes can be classified into one of the six categories shown in (Fig 3).

The category "questionable" contains skeptical answers, and it is debatable whether the respondent has understood the question (Kano et al. 1984). It was suggested by Berger et al. (1993) that cells 2-2 and 4-4 in the Kano evaluation table be changed from "I" to "Q," since they believe, for example, that a requirement that is rated as must-be functional cannot simultaneously be rated as must-be dysfunctional. Lee and Newcomb (1997) classify five combinations of the 25 options as questionable (cell 1-1, 1-2, 2-1, 2-2, and 5-5) [2].

In the last section of the questionnaire, the quality of all the attributes identified and classified, then by using Kendall tau to test its effect on women's impulsive buying and preferences are evaluated.

Figure 2: A pair of Consumer Requirement Questions in a Kano Questionnaire

<p>Function Question: How do you feel if that feature is present in the product?</p>	<p>1. I like it that way. 2. It must be that way. 3. I am neutral. 4. I can live with it that way. 5. I dislike it that way.</p>
<p>Dysfunction Questions: How do you feel if that feature is not present in the product?</p>	<p>1. I like it that way. 2. It must be that way. 3. I am neutral. 4. I can live with it that way. 5. I dislike it that way.</p>

Figure 3: Kano Evaluation Table (adapted from Berger et al. (1993)).

<p>Quality attributes →</p> <p>↓</p>		Dysfunction				
		1. Like	2. Must - be	3. Neutral	4. Live with	5. Dislike
Function	1. Like	Q	A	A	A	O
	2. Must - be	R	I	I	I	M
	3. Neutral	R	I	I	I	M
	4. Live with	R	I	I	I	M
	5. Dislike	R	R	R	R	M

A: Attractive

O: One-dimensional

M: Must-be

I: Indifferent

R: Revers

Q: Questionable

this quality attribute merely prevents the customer from being dissatisfied [3].

3. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The first part of the analysis was concerned with classifying the religious symbols & image quality attributes according to the theory of attractive quality. Each quality attribute was classified according to the evaluation table into either attractive (A), one-dimensional (O), must-be (M), indifferent (I), reverse (R), or questionable (Q). Lee and Newcomb (1997) introduced two measurements to aid in the classification of quality attributes: category strength and total strength. Category strength is defined as the percent difference of the highest category above the next-highest category. Total strength is defined as the total percentage of attractive, one-dimensional, and must-be responses [3].

A calculation of an average (better and worse), without losing the quality dimension's attractive, one-dimensional, and must-be attributes, was performed as suggested by Berger et al. (1993). These averages state whether customer satisfaction can be increased by meeting a certain quality attribute or whether fulfilling

$$Better = \frac{A + O}{A + O + M + I} \quad Worse = \frac{O + M}{A + O + M + I}$$

The positive better numbers indicate that customer satisfaction will increase by providing a quality attribute and the negative worse numbers indicate that customer satisfaction will decrease by not providing a quality attribute [3]. The maximum value of better and worse is 1. The closer the value is to 1, the greater the influence on customer satisfaction. A value of about 0 signifies that a certain quality attribute has little influence on customer satisfaction [6].

In the analysis, a Kano variable containing the classification of quality attributes was used as a dependent variable, while the demographic variables, such as gender, age, and family, were used as independent variables. The below table 1 shows an overview of the religious symbols & image quality attributes of packaging design. Furthermore, table 2 shows the correlation between demographic factors with

religious symbols & image quality attributes as a graphical design elements based on Kendall's tau test.

Table 1. An Overview of the Visual Merchandising Quality Attributes in Store Design on Impulsive Buying Behavior for Women's Clothing

Preferred Visual Merchandising Attributes in Store Design	Frequency Distribution on "Total Strength" Evaluation & Frequency Distribution of CRI of Study Variables							Total (%)	QA	B	W
	A	O	M	I	R	Q					
Store Layout	7.84	27.17	49.33	15.5	0.16	0	100	M	0.35	0.76	
Mannequins	35	14.84	8.17	24.83	17	0.16	100	A	0.60	0.27	
Point of purchase display	21.67	17.5	10.84	35.67	14.16	0.16	100	I	0.45	0.33	
Atmospherics	14.4	25.3	35.2	23.1	2	0	100	M	0.40	0.61	
Lighting	35.5	15.7	26.3	19.5	3	0	100	A	0.52	0.43	
Music	51.2	11.82	16.18	18.60	2.20	0	100	A	0.64	0.28	
Scent	41.8	16.6	27.5	12.1	2	0	100	A	0.59	0.45	
Window display	16.5	21.7	37	22.14	2.66	0	100	M	0.39	0.60	
Colour	27	17.3	17.36	30.84	7.34	0.16	100	I	0.47	0.37	
Graphics	20.34	26.16	16	29.16	8.34	0	100	I	0.51	0.45	
Photography & signage	39.6	21.3	17.6	15.4	6.1	0	100	A	0.64	0.41	
Seasonal displays	43.9	23	24.3	8.8	0	0	100	I	0.66	0.47	
Fashion trends	5.4	21.8	60	12	1	0.16	100	M	0.27	0.82	

Table 2. An Overview of Kendall's tau Correlation Coefficient between Visual Merchandising Factors in Store Design and women's Impulsive Buying Behavior

	Visual Merchandising										Ph,S	SD	FT
	SL	Ma	P	A	L	Mu	S	WD	C	G			
Impulsive Buying Behavior	.69*	.38*	.46	.70*	.71*	.60*	.114	.81*	.53	.65*	.77*	.89*	.81*

* Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (1-tailed).

The Kendall's tau findings, describes the significant correlation between women's impulsive buying behavior with all of the visual merchandising factors in store design except of "point of purchase display", "scent" and "color". This means that between these variables of visual merchandising and its impact on women's impulse behavior for buying clothing, there is no significant relationship.

4. CONCLUSION

Store visual merchandising is an important factor that contribute to the uniqueness of a store. Visual merchandising of a store convey several messages about the store to the consumers. Thus, quality of store visual merchandising plays a much more effective role in impulsive buying. This matter will be double important

when we have women's clothing store and we plan to stimulate their impulse purchase.

The results of this study showed a wide range of women's customer preferences in the store visual merchandising design according to Kano's attractive theory. Focus on the study results certainly suggests that the store design has many delicate matter which vendors should consider them for achieving greater success.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

First of all, we are grateful to The Almighty God for establishing us to complete this research. We take this opportunity to record our sincere thanks to parents for their support and unceasing encouragement.

REFERENCES

1. Alireza, K., and Hasti, Y., (2011). "Evaluating Effective Factors on Consumer Impulse Buying Behavior", Asian Journal of Business Management Studies 2 (4): 174-181.

2. Dadras, Abbas (2015, a). Impact of Label Information and Typography in Packaging Design on Consumer Behaviour in the Lens of KANO'S Attractive Quality Theory, *International Research Journal of Marketing and Economics*, 2(4): 16-31.
3. Dadras, Abbas (2015, b). Impact of Shapes in Packaging Design on Consumer Behaviour in the Lens of KANO'S Attractive Quality Theory, *International Journal of Scientific Research and Management Studies (IJSRMS)*, 2(1): 78-86
4. Jong Sung Kim (2013). A study on the effect that V.M.D (Visual Merchandising Design) in store has on purchasing products, *International Journal of Smart Home*, 7(4): 217-223.
5. Jungmi Oh, Susan S. Fiorito, Hira Cho, Charles F. Hofacker (2007). Effects of design factors on store image and expectation of merchandise quality in web-based stores, *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*, 3(4): 2-12.
6. Löfgren, M., & Witell, L. (2005). Kano's Theory of Attractive Quality and Packaging. *Quality Management Journal*, 12(3): 7-20.
7. Mai Ngoc Khuong and Ta Bao Tran (2015). Factors Affecting Impulse Buying toward Fashion Products in Ho Chi Minh City — A Mediation Analysis of Hedonic Purchase, *International Journal of Trade, Economics and Finance*, 6 (4): 223-229.
8. Tauseef Ahmad (2011), the Impulse Buying Behavior of Consumes For the FMCG Products in Jodhpur", *Australian Journal of Basic and Applied Sciences*, 5(11): 1704-1710